

The Psychosocial Effects of Sickle Cell Anaemia Among Couples in Ekiti State, Southwestern Nigeria

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Abstract

The function of the normal red blood cell is to transport oxygen with the help of haemoglobin while, sickle-shaped red blood cells are dehydrated, rigid and fragile causing blockage small blood vessels leading to vaso- occlusion, intravascular hemolysis and series of life threatening disorders [1]. The inheritance of homozygous sickle haemoglobin (HbS) is in accord with Mendelian laws. According to Mendelian laws, if carriers (AS) marry each other they will probably produce a sickler (SS) in ratio 1(SS): 2(AS): 1(AA) [2]. This is a descriptive study among secondary school teachers aiming at their knowledge level and specifically identifies the Socioeconomic effects of sickle cells diseased (SCD) on couples. Three hundred (300) participants were selected using simple random sampling Technique. The study instruments are a pre tested, validated, self-administered structured questionnaires. Data were analyzed using statistical package for social sciences (SPSS) version 20; results were presented in tables and percentages. The results show that participants have good knowledge on SCD (83.3%), while 50% knows that it is an inherited blood disorders, 66.67 % knows that it can be detected via blood test. Majority of the respondents (93%) affirmed that genotype can influence their choice of partners to marry despite love and affection towards their partners. The study recommends more public health education and training to enable patients to receive optimum care for the treatment and prevention of SCD and more specialist centers should be established in high-risk communities.

Introduction

Sickle cell disease (SCD) is an inherited blood disorder caused by abnormal hemoglobin [3]. The "sickling" of the red blood cells, reduce the oxygen carrying capacity of the hemoglobin [4]. This disorder affects all parts of the human body and differs widely among individuals [5]. The sickles haped red blood cells described by Herrick caused several complications, including chronic anemia, vaso-occlusive pain episodes, ischemic organ damage, infections, small stature, and delayed puberty [4].

Sickle cell disease affects millions of people throughout the world, and it is found to be the most common blood disorder among families whose ancestors came from

Sub Saharan Africa, South America, Cuba, Central America, Saudi Arabia, India, and the Mediterranean regions [3]. Studies indicate that approximately 1 in 12 Igbos are heterozygous for the disorder, and approximately 1 in 500 2 Igbo newborns are diagnosed annually with SCD [6]. Vaso-occlusive episodes have been repeatedly reported as the most common cause for hospitalization of SCD patients, representing \$475 million in annual health care expenditures and \$75,000 in hospitalization costs and acute sickle cell pain has been described by patients as being more severe than post-operative pain and as intense as cancer pain [7]. Recent studies suggest that children born with the SS genotype have a significantly median age of 1.9 years

More Information

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to first dactylitis episodes, compared to 3.9 years with those who are born with the SC genotype [8]. Also, in terms of episodes, 40% to 50% of those children experience one pain episode per month, while 10% of other school-age children experience pain episodes more than twice a month [8].

So far there seems to be no known cure for sickle cell anaemia as this disease can only be prevented by giving the individual who wish to marry, genetic counseling. Blood tests are usually carried out to determine the genotype of couples wishing to marry. A carrier of the gene “SS” can protect his children by marrying an “AA” genotype individual. In this case, their children are either AA or AS all of whom are healthy [1]. The study will also help to increase awareness of checking genotype before marriage, thereby reducing the scourge of SCD. This will also help in reducing premature death among children and increase life expectancy. The aimed at identify the knowledge level and socio-economic effects of sickle cell anaemia on couples.

Research Methodology

The study is a descriptive cross sectional study design with systematic random sampling technique, among public secondary school teachers in Ekiti state. The study instrument is a pretested, validated, structured, self-administered questionnaire. Ethical clearance was granted by the research and ethics committee of Open University Ado-Ekiti, study centre. Participation was voluntary, informed consent was obtained, confidentiality was maintained and the study was beneficence.

Sample and sampling procedure

Due to large size of the target population, the researcher used the Taro Yamane formula to arrive at the sample size for the study.

$$n = \frac{N}{1+N \cdot (e)^2} \tag{1}$$

$$n = \frac{30}{1+30 \cdot (0.05)^2} = \frac{30}{1+30 \cdot (0.0025)} = n = \frac{30}{1+0.75} = 27.9$$

The researcher approximated the sample population to 30 teachers per school.

Selection of the target school for the study

All ever married teachers in selected schools that agreed to participate in the study were included while critically ill teachers were excluded from the study. Data collected were collated, sorted and filtered to prevent error. The data were analysis with statistical package for social sciences (SPSS) version 20. The findings were presented with frequency tables and percentage.

Results

Table 1: Socio-Demographic Data

Socio demographic profile	Frequency N=300	Percentage N=100
Age		
21-30	150	50
31-40	100	33.33
≥ 41	50	16.67
Sex		
Male	120	40
Female	180	60
Ethnicity		
Yoruba	200	66.67
Hausa	50	16.67
Igbo	30	10
Others	20	6.67

The above table shows that most of the respondents are between 31- 40 years of age, female and of Yoruba ethnicity.

Table 2: Respondents’ Knowledge and Effects on Sickle Cell Diseases

Variable	Frequency N=300	Percentage N=100
Have you heard of SCD before?		
Yes	250	83.3
No	50	16.67
What is SCD?		
Inherited blood disorder	150	50
Infectious disease	50	16.67
Sexually Transmitted Disease	70	23.3
Fatal illness	30	10
Do you know how SCD is diagnosed?		
By blood test	200	66.67
Urinary test	80	26.67
I don’t know	20	6.67
Which of the following is a preventive measure for SCD?		
Medical Advice	200	66.67

Pre-marital screening	80	26.67
I don't know	20	6.67
Can your partner's genotype influence the decision to marry each other despite the love and affection?		
Yes	280	93.00
No	2	6.67

The above table shows that 83.3% % of the respondents are aware of SCD, while 50% knows that it is an inherited blood disorders,66.67 % knows that it can be detected via blood test. Most of the participants (66.7%) agreed that it can be prevented medical advice while 6.67% does not know the means of preventing SCD. Majority of the respondent (93%) said that genotype can influence their choice of partners to marry.

Discussion

SCD is a chronic, inherited blood disorders with no permanent cure. Majority of the respondents are aware of SCD while quite significant proportion are not aware despite their level of education as a teacher. About half of the respondent agreed with Sarojini and Umeh et al. identifying SCD as an inherited blood disorders while some still think that it is an infectious diseases that can spread through sexual and physical contact. Understanding the pathophysiology of SCD will help in preventing the disease rather than wasting resources on managing complication, in support with Prabhakan findings. Majority of the respondents affirmed that genotype can influence their choice of partners to marry despite the love and affection that they feel.

Conclusion

The scarcity of SCD research illustrates how our society fails to view sickle cell disease as a serious illness. Without awareness and a public outcry for a care and prevention, sickle cell disease will continue to be a silent killer to young men and women around the world.

Recommendation

More research on the public's general knowledge about this disease will help determine the areas where more education is needed on SCD. There is need to increase public awareness on care and prevention of SCD.

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